

MINI RESEARCH

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**Bitcoin ETFs, exploring the Emergence,
Impact, and Investment Potential of Bitcoin
ETFs.**

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1 ABSTRACT

This mini research focuses on investigating the emergence, impact, and investment potential of Bitcoin Exchange-Traded Funds (ETFs).

The approval of Bitcoin ETF finally occurred on January 10, 2024, after a decade of rejections, this has certainly changed the landscape of traditional financial systems but to what extent and how will this change affect the future of both the cryptocurrency and stock market industry.

The paper gives a brief introduction of what Bitcoin and Bitcoin ETFs are (**Anthony**), the volume of Bitcoin ETF in recent times and how it affected market trends(**Harshal**), its impact on the stock and the cryptocurrency markets(**Harshal**), the investment potential of Bitcoin ETFs (**Anthony**)

2 INTRODUCTION

Anthony) Diving into a brief introduction of what bitcoin and ETFs are, bitcoin is a digital currency, it originated in 2009, uses blockchain technology and has gradually become a prominent asset that has been gathering widespread attention from both retail and institutional investors.

ETFs on the other hand is a regulated financial tool that are able to give investors exposure to different classes of assets such as bonds, stocks etc which can be traded on the traditional stock market, bitcoin ETF as a regulated ETF product allows investors to gain exposure to the price movements of Bitcoin (BTC) without directly managing or holding it, the goal will be for individuals including institutional investors to invest in BTC, gain access to the price movement and make profits from it without the need of signing up for exchanges or holding BTC in wallets of any kind, they are publicly traded on traditional stock exchanges.

Harshal) As of the time of writing this research paper around March 2024, bitcoin ETF recorded it's highest volume at \$7.6 billion on February 28th, 2024 topping previous records, on its first day of listing, it recorded \$4.6 billion but did not have a significant impact on the cryptocurrency market for the first week.

Harshal) on the impact of BitcoinETF on the crypto industry, for the first time in history, bitcoin broke its previous all-time high before halving, this is largely accredited to the large inflow of bitcoinETF by institutional investors, writing on this is Hannah (2024), "Net flows into the 10 largest U.S. spot bitcoin funds reached \$2.2 billion in the week ended March 1, with more than \$2 billion of that going into BlackRock's iShares Bitcoin Trust (IBIT.O), according to LSEG data."

Anthony) while the mainstream adoption of cryptocurrency is still low as it faces significant regulatory issues and often misconduct from the crypto industry leaders, a recent example will be "Billionaire Changpeng Zhao and leading cryptocurrency exchange Binance pleaded guilty on Tuesday to federal charges in a watershed moment designed to bring order to the often-lawless crypto industry."(CNN news, 2023).

In terms of the investment potential of Bitcoin ETFs, some factors need to be considered such as risks, historical records, returns, diversification benefits and regulatory concerns.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Anthony) According to Omer(2024), 'Bitcoin users went from 222 million to 296 million between January 2023 and December 2023, while Ethereum users increased from 89 million to 124 million between the same time frame. Primary factors that fueled this growth include the rise of Bitcoin exchange-traded funds (ETFs), as well as the role of Bitcoin Ordinals protocols'.

This shows that at the moment, BitcoinETF has caused a sizable increase in the number of users of crypto(increased adoption) but this does not automatically translate to the investors making profit or tell us what the impact of this growth in terms of the good and bad to the industry, the regulatory issues raised, possible market manipulation, price dynamic of crypto products as a result of the inflow of BitcoinETF to the market.

Harshal) There are further important considerations to be looked into with BitcoinETF, despite the excitement it brought for crypto advocates, there has been and still is a regulatory concern for crypto in general, it took over a decade from 2003 till January 10, 2024, before the first 11 Spot Bitcoin ETFs got Approved, notes from Jeanne(2024) with focus on the SEC Chair Gary Gensler 'While we approved the listing and trading of certain spot bitcoin ETP shares today, we did not approve or endorse bitcoin. Investors should remain cautious about the myriad risks associated with Bitcoin and products whose value is tied to crypto,'.

These concerns still make lots of people regard cryptocurrency as a wildly volatile and unsafe asset class, they are also discouraged by the ever-present danger of cryptocurrency exploits, hacks, and scams, this begs the question, how open are retail and institutional investors when it comes to investing in Bitcoin ETFs after it's approval.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Anthony) Are retail or institutional investors open to investing in Bitcoin ETFs?

Harshal) Have retail or institutional investors trading bitcoin ETF been making profit or loss since its listing?

Anthony) What are the risks and returns associated with investing in Bitcoin ETFs?

Harshal) What is the influence of regulatory frameworks on Bitcoin ETFs.

Anthony) What impacts did the Bitcoin ETF make after its listing on the cryptocurrency market and economies in general?

OBJECTIVES

Anthony) Investigate how open retail or institutional investors are to investing in Bitcoin ETFs.

Harshal) Analyze the trading performance of Bitcoin since the listing of Bitcoin ETF to determine if there have been profits or incurring losses.

Anthony) Access returns and risks of investing in bitcoin ETF, a closer look will be taken at factors such as historical performance data, volatility, and market trends.

Harshal) Examine regulatory influence on bitcoin ETF, a closer look into factors such as why it took time to get approval, the approval processes, regulatory changes and compliance requirements.

Anthony) Evaluate the impacts of bitcoin ETF on the cryptocurrency market and wider economy after its listing taking a closer look at parameters such as recent investors' behavior, recent market dynamics, recent regulatory responses, and economic indicators.

LITERATURE REVIEW

BitcoinETFs are securities that investors buy or sell throughout the day on the stock exchange, these BitcoinETFs are subjected to regulations which encourage investors as cryptocurrency has been largely subjected to market manipulations often, projects have been found to misappropriate or manipulate investor's money as in the cases of Sam of FTX, Do Kwon of Terraform Labs including recently, CZ of Binance, so the approval of bitcoin ETFs is certainly a welcome development

The first set of 11 BitcoinETF that was approved was on January 10, 2024.

Name	Ticker	Fee (after Waiver)	Waiver Details	Exchange	Most Recent Filing	Custodian
Bitwise Bitcoin ETP Trust (Re-filing)	BITB	0.0% (0.20%)	6 Months &/or \$1 Billion	NYSE	1/9/24	Coinbase
ARK 21Shares Bitcoin ETF (Re-filing)	ARKB	0.0% (0.25%)	6 Months &/or \$1 Billion	CBOE	1/9/24	Coinbase
Invesco Galaxy Bitcoin ETF (Re-filing)	BTCO	0.0% (0.39%)	6 Months &/or \$5 Billion	CBOE	1/9/24	Coinbase
Wisdomtree Bitcoin Trust (Re-filing)	BTCW	0.0% (0.30%)	6 Months &/or \$1 Billion	CBOE	1/9/24	Coinbase
iShares Bitcoin Trust	IBIT	0.20% (0.30%)	12 Months &/or \$5 Billion	Nasdaq	1/9/24	Coinbase
VanEck Bitcoin Trust (Re-filing)	HODL	0.25%	None	CBOE	1/9/24	Gemini
Franklin Bitcoin ETF	EZBC	0.29%	None	CBOE	1/9/24	Coinbase
Fidelity Wise Origin Bitcoin Trust (Re-filing)	FBTC	0.39%	None	CBOE	1/9/24	Fidelity
Valkyrie Bitcoin Fund (Re-filing)	BRRR	0.49%	None	CBOE	1/9/24	Coinbase
Hashdex Bitcoin ETF (Strategy Change)	DEFI	0.90%	None	NYSE	12/26/23	BitGo
Grayscale Bitcoin Trust (Re-file) Conversion	GBTC	1.5%	None	NYSE	1/9/24	Coinbase

Source: Bloomberg Intelligence, SEC.gov

List of 11 spot bitcoin ETF issuers with updated fees. Source: Bloomberg analyst James Seyffart

We cannot talk about how profitable investments will be in Bitcoin ETF without discussing Bitcoin itself as the ETF product returns are based on the price actions of Bitcoin, Bitcoin seems to be gradually going in an uptrend movement and lots of factors seem to be playing

out to cause this:

Bitcoin shares some characteristics with gold, There primary value is due to the fact that they are scarce and costly to extract, again for Bitcoin, there is also the concept of “Halving” which is explained below:

When writing a block, a miner credits themselves with an amount of bitcoin, called the block subsidy. This amount changes: Approximately every 4 years, the automatic reward for producing a block is cut in half (Warren, 2023).

In addition to this, bitcoin ETF has steadily shown that with a high inflow, the price of Bitcoin steadily rises, this will be backed with empirical evidence in this research work, another is the store of value of bitcoin, if this belief holds true for an increasing number of people, we could keep seeing an increase in the price of Bitcoin:

And so we return to Venezuela again: where the state currency has long since lost its trust and its value storage function, people are increasingly trusting that Bitcoin can ‘store’ value. Better even: as it momentarily looks, the digital currency can even increase value in the long run (Erlmeier, 2021).

Nevertheless, other factors can also lead to loss of investors’ money such as volatility of bitcoin and speculation, a counter to the argument that it could be a store of value is also presented below:

While store of value remains a hopeful use case designed for residents of nations undergoing hyperinflation to protect their value, in practice this will always face the same speculative cycles. If people start to place their money into Bitcoin, financial institutions who are paying attention will front-run the movement and join the speculative frenzy, only to sell when the frenzy runs its course. For the time being, this appears unavoidable. (Warren, 2023).

Methodology

Our research adopts a **quantitative** approach, we are interested in studying BitcoinETF where we start with well-defined research questions, examine current literature dating from the time period of the year ‘2020’ upwards, we develop a conceptual framework and dive into data collections.

Data collection is secondary, well-structured and will be collected from ETF databases which can be found here: [Link to BitcoinETF Database](#) (VettaFi, 2024), the latest updated dataset will be extracted from here which is a reputable ETF database website that constantly monitors bitcoin ETF statistics, and a quantitative data analysis will be done which will involve using Python for data analysis, the analysis will also involve correlation analysis, descriptive statistics, with a regression modelling to check the relationship between key market indicators such as Bitcoin price with Bitcoin ETF.

The structure for this is below:

Step 1: Research Questions

Step 2: Literature review

Step 3: Define the Conceptual Framework

Step 4: Secondary Data Collection

Step 5: Data processing and analysis using Python, regression modelling.

Step 6: Result collection

Step 7: Final findings and conclusion

MARKET OVERVIEW FOR BITCOIN

Bitcoin founded in 2009 resulted in the concept of digital currency, it makes use of blockchain technology, it features peer-to-peer transactions, over time, it has gained grounds as a store of value, attracting investors who are guiding against inflation and retailers who mostly seem to be interested in making huge returns, Armstrong also notes that “The vast majority of the people in the market now were attracted to the technology because they see an opportunity to make money and they want to achieve financial freedom” (Armstrong, 2023).

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic is expected to play a vital role in driving the growth of the Bitcoin market over the forecast period. Bitcoin and Ethereum are utilized as alternative investments and appeared to outperform other assets while dealing with the negative impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on stock markets. (grandviewresearch, 2024)

Currently, the market valuation of Bitcoin is above \$1 trillion which is huge and shows diverse interest from both institutions and retailers, according to CNN, “Following bitcoin’s gains in 2023, investors have returned in droves in recent weeks, pushing the asset’s market capitalization above \$1 trillion for the first time since its 2021” (CNN, 2024)

Another factor affecting the rise of Bitcoin is that it is a secure network, more than 18 million miners are participating in securing it.

Bitcoin has equally had its share of crises such as in early 2014 when it survived the closure of what was then the most successful and biggest cryptocurrency exchange website which was “Mt. Gox”, leaked document indicates that a loss of 74,000 BTC which was worth around 40 million dollars had occurred, it was a turbulent time for both investors and retailers who were vested in it, it was majorly at this point that governments began to pass regulations.

Existing Literature on Bitcoin ETFs

ETFs since 2014 has emerged as popular mean of investment tool for portfolios, during this time SPDR SPY 500 ETF, which is a benchmark ETF has shown 8% of growth with 4% of volatility (e.g., Huang and Lin 2011; Miralles-Quiros et al. 2019), even if it is more moderate performance compared to Bitcoin with a high sharp ratio of 0.05. the SPY ETFs and same like it offers cost-effective access to commodities, stocks, bonds, currencies and macroeconomic factors. Therefore, Huang and Lin are saying that Bitcoin ETFs can be seen as a good investment tool to have a great return.

ETFs belong to the fastest growing investment products worldwide (Liebi, Luca J. 2020). Within 15 years, total assets invested in ETFs have increased 20 times, reaching over \$3.7 trillion at the end of 2018. Increasing demand for passive investments, mixed with high liquidity and low transaction costs, are key advantages of ETFs compared to their closest substitutes such as traditional index funds. Besides the continuous growth of ETFs, the crash in 2010 triggered detailed investigations by regulators on how ETFs affect the financial market.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework will be a representation of the relationship between my variables which will be dependent and independent variables.

First, a visual representation of the relationship between my key variables is shown below, this is based on my research questions.

Key Concepts:

Investment Potential of Bitcoin ETFs: this represents the degree of confidence investors and retailers have in this product to purchase it, it correlates to the possible profitability that could come from investing in it.

Investor behaviour:

A good investor knows that decisions must be made upon facts, historical data, market research, current market conditions, and many other factors (Armstrong, 2023).

Unfortunately, the above does not hold true at all times, sometimes, 'emotions' come into play often, investor behaviour refers to the decisions, actions, and psychological factors that come into play when investors engage, assets, financial markets and investment opportunities.

Market Dynamics: these represent factors that cause changes and fluctuations in the financial market such as price movement, sudden announcements that lead to either a huge sell-off or buy-off, supply and demand for assets, pumps and dumps, whales activities etc.

Price of Bitcoin: Most times, an increase in the price of bitcoin has always led to retailers' interests and affects investors' behaviours as well in investing more in BitcoinETF as this directly translates to profits if bought at a reasonably lower price.

Regulatory Framework: as an IV, this can define a set of parameters to check the compliance of institutions invested in BitcoinETFs to regulatory requirements.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

After collecting the dataset of BitcoinETFs which was last updated as of 8th of April,2024, we made selections of variables from the columns in the dataset as below:

Dependent Variable (DV): YTD Price Change

Independent Variables (IVs): Total Assets and Avg. Daily Volume

The above shows a heat map, the highest correlation to 'YTD price change' is 'Total assets'(0.34) and 'Avg. Daily Volume'(0.38).

YTD Price Change: defines the "Year-to-Date Price Change" which is the percentage change in the price of each BitcoinETF product, a simple example for this will be, if the price YTD price change is 5%, it means the BitcoinETF product has increased by 5% since the beginning of the year up until the current date and if it's -5%, it goes vice versa and means it has decreased.

Total Assets: defines the overall value of each ETF.

Avg. Daily Volume: defines the average number of trades of the ETF product in a day.

We will be exploring the relationship between the dependent Variables and independent Variables by performing a regression analysis, there will be a model estimation with the use of Python in a Jupiter notebook, and the results will be interpreted using measures such as R-squared.

The code used for this data analysis can be found in the GitHub repository: [Link to Repository](#). (Tony, 2024)

OLS Regression Results						
Dep. Variable:	YTD Price Change	R-squared:	0.156			
Model:	OLS	Adj. R-squared:	0.068			
Method:	Least Squares	F-statistic:	1.760			
Date:	Wed, 10 Apr 2024	Prob (F-statistic):	0.199			
Time:	00:26:26	Log-Likelihood:	-2.4023			
No. Observations:	22	AIC:	10.80			
Df Residuals:	19	BIC:	14.08			
Df Model:	2					
Covariance Type:	nonrobust					
	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
const	0.2902	0.066	4.417	0.000	0.153	0.428
Total Assets	9.756e-12	1.84e-11	0.530	0.602	-2.87e-11	4.82e-11
Avg. Daily Volume	1.305e-08	1.38e-08	0.943	0.358	-1.59e-08	4.2e-08
Omnibus:	2.815	Durbin-Watson:	2.448			
Prob(Omnibus):	0.245	Jarque-Bera (JB):	1.541			
Skew:	0.633	Prob(JB):	0.463			
Kurtosis:	3.278	Cond. No.	5.11e+09			

Notes:

- [1] Standard Errors assume that the covariance matrix of the errors is correctly specified.
- [2] The condition number is large, 5.11e+09. This might indicate that there are strong multicollinearity or other numerical problems.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

We will put focus on the R-squared (R^2) value known as the coefficient of determination, it measured the proportion of the variance in the IV (YTD price change) to the DV (Total assets and Avg. daily volume).

From the OLS regression results in the diagram above, the R-squared value is 0.156, this shows that only around 15.6% of the variance in YTD Price Change can be explained by the independent variables, this is to be expected as there is still quite a number of DV that has not been captured by the dataset such as bitcoin price, certain market sentiments, regulatory frameworks, events that causes panic sale or buy actions, bear/bull market conditions, market manipulation, whales' activities.

In actual reality, lots of other DVs are vital to further this research and expand it.

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